

Insights on Teaching AI at Scale: Data-Driven Feedback for Learner-Centered Improvement

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Abstract. Teaching Artificial Intelligence (AI) at scale presents unique challenges in designing effective, learner-centered educational experiences. This paper explores how data-driven feedback from learners in a wide-scale platform is used as a reference in mapping the strengths and weaknesses perceived by learners in Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) on AI.

Using responses based on post-course surveys, we use statistics and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to uncover recurring themes in learners' choices and open-ended comments. The findings reveal that different demographics have different course perceptions, and in general, integrating interactive content is one of the attractions to increase learners' engagement in completing their courses. These insights offer the opportunities to refine MOOC structure and content for a more inclusive and engaging learning environment.

This study contributes to the growing body of research in AI education, especially in large-scale online formats, by demonstrating how analysis of user feedback can pinpoint actionable insights. The results of this exploratory study can provide recommendations to course designers for preparing AI education content across different user segment profiles to continuously improve AI-focused MOOCs and better meet the evolving needs of learners.

Keywords: MOOCs · Artificial Intelligence Education · Latent Dirichlet Allocation · Topic Modelling · Interactive Content · Learning Analytics.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly expanding and being applied across various fields. As a result, there is a growing demand for educational platforms that can provide AI education at scale. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have become a key medium for meeting this need. With their flexibility and accessibility, MOOCs make quality AI education widely available by lowering barriers to entry for learners worldwide.

Despite the advantages offered by MOOCs, they also face a major challenge common to online course providers: low participation rates among enrolled learners. High dropout rates remain a common issue, especially when strong conceptual understanding is involved, such as in AI courses. Unlike traditional

classroom settings or small-scale e-learning environments where instructors can adapt in real-time to learners' needs, MOOCs rely heavily on pre-designed content and offer limited interaction with instructors, usually through forums and Q&A sessions. To bridge this gap, instructors often integrate interactive content (IC) such as quizzes, coding exercises, and interactive videos to improve learner engagement and comprehension.

Even with the adoption of interactive content, its actual impact on learner experience, particularly in AI-focused MOOCs, remains under-researched. While previous studies have examined engagement metrics related to interactive videos [5, 10, 12, 16], as well as other interactive elements [4, 13, 2], learner perception is an area that requires further exploration. Insights from open-ended survey responses can reveal nuances that predefined survey feedback might overlook. However, processing large-scale responses poses another significant challenge.

This study aims to uncover how learners perceive IC in AI-focused MOOCs on KI-Campus by applying topic modeling techniques to large-scale learner feedback. We use Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to extract key themes from post-course survey responses across multiple AI courses. By analyzing topics emerging from positive feedback and comparing them across learner demographics, such as gender and age, which have been previously associated with different engagement, motivation, and preferences [3, 6, 7], we identify aspects of IC that enhance the learning experience and suggest improvements for instructors, for more inclusive courses.

Our research provides data-driven insights to support designing more effective AI MOOC content. Using topic modeling, we highlight learners' priorities while addressing their needs. This is particularly valuable for course creators, instructors, and MOOC providers seeking to optimize AI course design to better align with learner expectations. We hope our findings deepen our understanding of learner needs and offer practical recommendations to improve online AI education at scale.

2 Related Work

2.1 Interactive Content in AI-Education MOOCs

In its development, interactive content such as interactive videos, various interactive quizzes, and coding exercises are adopted by AI-focused MOOCs and have been proven to increase learner engagement in large-scale online education settings [5]. By actively involving learners in the learning process to replace interaction in real-world classroom settings, this element helps bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical applications [4, 2].

On the KI-Campus platform, IC has been used extensively and has become one of the important points in the guide for instructors to design a course. Previous research on KI-Campus shows how courses that use IC have higher engagement rates than those that do not [15]. Other study also shows how the benefits of strategically placing IC as a self-assessment tool embedded directly into course materials significantly impact users [14].

As an evaluation and process to improve the quality of content, especially related to the use of IC provided in delivering teaching about AI, it is important to explore user feedback in a user-centered learning experience approach, which requires a special approach to get good insight in large-scale text feedback analysis [9].

2.2 Text Analysis and Topic Modelling in Educational Context

Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques have been found to be effective for analyzing educational data, especially in understanding the learner experience from feedback [9]. LDA, which is a topic modeling NLP technique, is able to explore latent themes in large text datasets [1, 8]. As an unsupervised learning method, LDA is suitable for this case, where we cluster themes from an unlabeled dataset derived from open-ended questions in a survey. With the use of this LDA technique, it is expected that data-driven insights will provide themes to be used as evaluation materials for instructors in designing courses or improving existing content within the framework of AI-Education MOOC.

3 Methodology

In this section, we describe the data used, the LDA topic modeling, and the qualitative analysis used to generate the information that will be discussed in the results section.

3.1 Data Collection and Preprocessing

The data was collected from responses taken from the post-course survey, focusing on 40 courses that used interactive elements extensively as part of the course content as well as a tool for self-assessment tests.

The open-ended question from the said post-course survey is intended to evaluate the course from the learner’s point of view; it serves to evaluate the positive aspects of the course, especially from the integration of interactive elements in course content.

The selected courses are based on several categories, such as AI in Education, Data Literacy, AI in Medicine, Foundation of AI, Machine Learning, and Societal Aspect of AI.

The dataset consists of textual feedback, which will then be paired with statistical data from the same survey to provide a comprehensive overview. It will also be viewed based on the age and gender demographics of the survey participants for comparison. These responses are then collected in CSV and combined into a single dataset for analysis. Prior to analysis, missing responses were removed to ensure data integrity.

To prepare the textual data for analysis, we applied Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques using NLTK and Gensim libraries by executing several steps, including lowercasing, tokenization, stopword removal, punctuation, and

number removal, and converting into bag-of-words representation, before being ready to be consumed in the LDA process.

3.2 Latent Dirichlet Allocation Topic Modelling

To identify key themes from course participants' responses, we employ LDA, which is a topic modeling method that assumes each document (user response) consists of a mixture of topics, and each topic is represented by a distribution of words.

Due to the nature of LDA, which is an unsupervised method, the measure is done by testing the model on several configurations to see the optimal results. Several key parameters are considered in the LDA model configuration, including adjusting the topic numbers and the number of iterations until we get the highest topic coherence score, following the method applied in previous research by Rödel et al. (2015) [11]. A relevance threshold is also applied when interpreting topic proportions. We use a threshold weight equal to 0.05, which means a topic is only considered to exist in a document if its probability of occurrence is above 5%. This is done to avoid the presence of unrepresentative topics and improve the accuracy of the presence of topics in the dataset. Then, using pyLDAvis, these results will be re-evaluated manually to see the distance relationship between each topic cluster created.

3.3 Data Analysis

To explore the emerging themes, in addition to directly analyzing the themes generated from the LDA modeling process, the resulting themes are also viewed in terms of demographics, in this case, in terms of gender and age group. This is to analyze the differences and similarities of the themes that appear in each user group. With the application of LDA and going deeper into different demographic user groups, a broader understanding of the interactivity role in MOOCs will be obtained.

4 Results

4.1 Overall theme

When running LDA in the post-course survey on the positive response section of the question "What did you particularly like about the course?", we analyzed 1,312 responses after cleaning and preprocessing the data. This resulted in several dominant theme clusters, as shown in Table 1. The most common opinion highlights content variety and interactive videos as the most preferred interactive elements, particularly as test aids.

Interactive videos in this context refer to video content created using H5P, enriched with embedded interactive features such as quizzes, clickable hotspots, and pop-up text. These elements act as self-assessment tools, allowing learners to reinforce key concepts as they watch and interact with the video.

Other key themes related to interactive content include positive user experiences with various interactive elements (topics 2, 3, 5, 8, and 9), as well as the importance of course structure, content quality, and best practices in mastering AI concepts (topics 4, 6, 7, and 10).

Table 1: Overall Theme Feedback

Topic	Top Words	Theme	Prop.
1	everything, topics, easy, well, variety	General positive feedback and topic variety	34.32
2	videos, tasks, interactive, short, video	Interactive video and task-based learning	32.54
3	tests, self, quiz, time, informative	Self-assessment and informative quizzes	14.19
4	well, structured, information, course, explanations	Course structure and explanation quality	14.12
5	good, structure, videos, course, quizzes	Course design and assessment format	13.74
6	content, good, language, learning, course	Learning content and language clarity	12.63
7	short, examples, exercises, application, units	Concise examples and applied exercises	11.89
8	questions, good, videos, interviews, ai	Interview content and AI topics	11.89
9	graphics, examples, clear, applications, jupyter	Visual examples and practical tools	11.74
10	understandable, comprehensive, topics, course, overview	Topic overview and comprehensibility	9.21

4.2 Themes based on Demographics

From the next two tables (Table 2 and Table 3), we gain insight into several similar positive themes among both male and female users. The topic structure has the biggest proportion for both groups. Self-testing and interactive elements are frequently mentioned as valuable tools (topics 1, 2, 4, 5, 9, and 10 for males, topic 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, and 8 for females). Specifically, videos are seen as an effective learning medium by both. Both male and female learners also gave positive feedback on the clear structure and well-organized content. However, there are subtle differences in preferences, most notably in the learning approach. Male learners have a higher proportion of preference for structured assessment and content overview, while females prefer variety, depth, and clarity.

Table 2: Male Response

Topic	Top Words	Theme	Prop.
1	structure, self, tests, clear, good	Structured self-assessment	19.63
2	videos, good, course, interviews, questions	Video content and interactive elements	18.21
3	easy, understand, tasks, ai, video	Ease of understanding and AI content	14.51
4	well, graphics, examples, topics, course	Visual and well-presented content	14.08
5	good, quizzes, learning, comprehensive, many	Good quizzes and comprehensive learning	12.52
6	structured, well, topic, presentation, understandable	Structured presentation and clarity	12.52
7	content, learning, time, topics, online	Learning content and time management	12.23
8	everything, informative, practical, good, overview	Informative and practical overview	12.23
9	topics, good, lecturers, presented, variety	Variety in lecture presentation	12.09
10	ai, short, learning, video, design	Short AI videos and design focus	9.82

Table 3: Female Response

Topic	Top Words	Theme	Prop.
1	everything, examples, structure, different, application	Examples and structural variety	16.40
2	self, tests, videos, liked, way	Self-tests and video engagement	14.59
3	well, content, structured, course, explanations	Well-structured and explained content	14.23
4	topics, videos, variety, short, topic	Topic diversity and short videos	13.69
5	videos, quizzes, material, course, good	Video and quiz-based materials	13.15
6	questions, quiz, video, detailed, tests	Detailed quizzes and video tests	12.25
7	explained, ai, many, good, understandable	Clear explanations and AI-related topics	12.25
8	well, knowledge, programming, interactive, structure	Programming knowledge and interactivity	10.99
9	structure, graphics, well, easy, understand	Visual structure and ease of understanding	10.63
10	varied, learning, design, yes, elements	Varied learning elements and design	9.91

5 Theme in Different Age Groups

From Table 4, 5, and 6, we can infer some similarities across the three age groups, as all of them agree that video is the most useful medium, with all of them having a positive experience with the interactive and engaging video content. In addition, the interactive elements that served as tools for self-test assessment were considered very valuable, and they also appreciated the well-structured course content and sufficient practical exercises in the AI course they attended.

Interestingly, there are key differences in the perceptions of each age group. Young learners prefer short, engaging videos, varied interactive quizzes, and example-based learning. Mid-career learners focus on structured content, practical learning, and comprehensive explanations. Meanwhile, older learners value easy-to-follow, well-timed content, structured progression, and diverse explanation.

Table 4: Theme for Age Group 18–30 Years Old

Topic	Top Words	Theme	Prop.
1	videos, information, simple, well, structure	Informative and well-structured videos	18.63
2	everything, liked, learning, different, many	General appreciation and learning variety	15.21
3	self, tests, videos, test, quiz	Self-testing and assessment content	13.88
4	videos, short, good, well, quizzes	Short and effective video content	13.50
5	interactive, graphics, videos, explanation, elements	Interactive elements and visual explanations	12.74
6	examples, video, application, design, varied	Practical examples and varied design	12.17
7	content, information, knowledge, course, easy	Accessible and informative content	11.60
8	topics, material, programming, well, overview	Programming topics and course overview	11.41
9	videos, learning, short, ai, different	Short videos and AI learning	8.56
10	learning, structure, course, good, clear	Course structure and learning clarity	8.37

6 Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Conclusion

This study analyzed post-course survey responses to evaluate learner engagement with interactive content in AI-related MOOCs. The results indicated that

Table 5: Theme for Age Group 30–50 Years Old

Topic	Top Words	Theme	Prop.
1	well, structured, tasks, presented, understandable	Well-structured tasks and clear presentation	16.98
2	structure, clear, good, language, broad	Clear structure and language diversity	15.73
3	topics, easy, variety, understand, speakers	Topic variety and ease of understanding	15.11
4	self, practical, tests, quiz, structure	Practical self-tests and structure	15.11
5	overview, good, examples, comprehensive, videos	Comprehensive overviews and examples	13.46
6	videos, content, topics, examples, liked	Engaging content with examples	12.84
7	videos, well, knowledge, course, explanations	Video explanations and course knowledge	12.01
8	well, ai, knowledge, content, course	AI knowledge and well-prepared content	10.77
9	everything, quizzes, course, topics, good	General positive feedback and quizzes	10.77
10	learning, structure, study, interactive, easy	Structured and interactive learning	8.28

Table 6: Theme for Age Group Above 50 Years Old

Topic	Top Words	Theme	Prop.
1	structure, clear, understandable, good, information	Clear structure and understandable information	16.33
3	well, varied, structured, course, questions	Well-structured and varied course content	15.99
2	good, presentation, course, videos, different	Good presentations and diverse course materials	13.95
4	videos, good, time, modules, texts	Video-based learning and modular content	13.61
9	easy, good, course, language, elements	Ease of understanding and language clarity	12.59
8	everything, structure, great, compact, units	Compact structure and overall satisfaction	10.20
5	short, content, video, learning, skills	Short video content for skill development	9.86
6	good, well, important, level, structuring	Important structural aspects and quality	8.50
7	examples, ai, helpful, supplement, application	AI examples and helpful supplements	8.50
10	well, videos, different, explanations, speakers	Different speakers and video explanations	7.48

interactive videos, particularly those enriched with self-testing features, were highly valued by learners. Another dominant theme that emerged showed that users valued well-structured courses, clear explanations, engaging multimedia elements, and tests significantly contributed to the positive learning experience.

Demographic analysis showed commonalities and differences across gender and age groups. While both male and female learners found interactive videos and self-testing beneficial, males preferred structured content and clarity, whereas females valued varied, engaging video content. Age-based analysis highlighted that younger learners favored short, engaging videos, mid-career learners preferred structured and practical content, and older learners appreciated easy-to-follow, well-paced learning materials, being the most dominant theme among others.

As an exploratory study, this finding emphasizes that even in a large-scale setup, it is important for content creators to consider user perception to differentiate learning approaches based on the target demographics they want to reach to obtain optimal engagement.

6.2 Future Work

Future research should focus on other user groups to see the different themes that emerge, as well as explore other open-ended questions to enrich our understanding of user needs in the context of AI-focused MOOCs. Additionally, research towards usability and accessibility improvement, especially on interactive content that is based on user preference, such as interactive video, can be prioritized and adjusted to the profile of most users enrolled in the course. This will certainly make MOOCs more inclusive and effective for a wider audience.

Acknowledgments. The Germany Federal Ministry of Education and Research (*Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung*) supported the work to produce this research.

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